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Project Coordinator: **Marc HUGER**, marc.huger@unilim.fr, IRCER

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Deliverable D3.1 - Thermochemical database of refractory minerals in H₂

Primary author:

Dr. Kinga KLIMA, Dr. Thorsten TONNESEN

Document contributor:

Cristian Daniel Bohorquez Moreno

Milena Amábilis Ribeiro Gomes

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1. Introduction

To prevent environmental disruption in the coming decades, CO₂ emissions must be reduced worldwide across different sectors. Those include the steel industry, which currently responds to 7 - 9 % of worldwide carbon emissions [1]. The industry is investigating different technologies for minimizing its environmental footprint, and the direct reduction of iron (DRI) has emerged as a potential solution. In the DRI technology, iron ores are typically pelletized and then reduced in the solid state, without melting, at temperatures in the range of 800 - 1050 °C. The sponge iron that is produced in this process is then generally converted into steel in an electric arc furnace (EAF). The DRI-EAF route is an alternative to the traditional method of reducing iron ores to produce pig iron in the blast furnace (BF), and then converting it into steel in the basic oxygen furnace (BOF). Compared with the BF-BOF route, the DRI-EAF route allows a substantial reduction in emissions. Typically, the reducing gas in this process is derived from coal or natural gas and presents a mix of CO and H₂ [2]. The current trend is to introduce hydrogen directly in the process, increasing the H₂/CO ratio, with the intention of reducing the CO₂ emissions in the process [3].

This will, however, bring new challenges for refractory materials. Hydrogen has the potential to reduce and corrode ceramics, but the thermodynamics, kinetics, and mechanism of the process are not fully understood [4]. A better comprehension of the effect of hydrogen on refractories is crucial, as refractory performance directly impacts the operation and efficiency of a DRI plant. In this context, this report will present a series of thermochemical calculations on the effect of hydrogen on refractories. The equilibrium of hydrogen with silica, alumina, mullite, magnesia, zirconia, mullite, and andalusite will be analysed, and in the case of silica, further simulations will be made to determine the effect of pressure, as well as of the presence of water in the atmosphere, on reduction. Thermodynamics is key for understanding corrosion, as it can tell which processes occur spontaneously and can therefore be expected to occur under a particular set of conditions.

2. Current knowledge

Only a limited number of thermodynamic analyses have been published regarding the effect of hydrogen on refractories. A very extensive investigation is described in a report by Misra, written in 1980 for NASA's Lewis Research Center [5]. Misra employed the SOLGASMIX-PV program and used thermodynamic data from different sources, including the JANAF Thermochemical Tables. As the study was conducted to support material selection for high-temperature propulsion systems in aerospace applications, it includes a large number of ceramic materials beyond those typically used in steelmaking, including SiC, Si₃N₄, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, mullite, ZrO₂, Y₂O₃, CaO, MgO, BeO, TiB₂, TiC, HfC, and

ZrC. The report calculates upper-temperature limits for the use of the different materials, defining it as the temperature for which the partial pressure of reduction products is in equilibrium with hydrogen at 1 atm in of 1 ppm, and examines the effect of temperature, pressure, and the presence of water vapour. In a more recent study from 2022, that also encompassed a range of ceramics, Li et al. calculated the equilibrium partial pressure of reduction products in the gas phase for the reaction of hydrogen with SiO_2 , MgO , Al_2O_3 , CaO , TiO_2 , and Fe_2O_3 , at temperatures from 1200 to 1800 °C [6]. Both studies allow to draw a comparison of the stability of the different oxides.

Simulations that have been made on specific systems also shed light on the effect of hydrogen on refractories. Gentile et al. used the TERRA thermodynamic software from the Bauman Moscow State Technical University to compare the activity of SiO_2 under hydrogen in three different systems:

- pure stoichiometric mullite;
- a sample containing 96.3 % alumina and 3.7 % mullite; and,
- high-purity alumina with minor amounts of SiO_2 impurities [7].

Interestingly, it was found that the SiO_2 shows the highest stability as an impurity and that it is more stable in the alumina-mullite system than in pure mullite. In a very recent publication from 2024, Leber et al. carried out thermodynamic simulations on FactSage 8.2 to support an experimental study of phosphate-bonded refractory materials based on corundum, fireclay, and magnesia [8]. It was found that, at temperatures around 1000 °C, large quantities of P_2O_3 are formed and, with an increase in temperature, further reduction to P was predicted by the simulation. This coincided with observation of the volatilization of phosphorous from the materials under experimental investigation. The thermodynamic simulations also show the formation of iron phosphides, both Fe_2P and Fe_3P . Those phases were likewise observed in the exposed samples via an XRD analysis, albeit not at the entire temperature range for which they had been predicted. They were only observed at the higher end of testing temperatures at 1500 °C. Combined with the trials, the calculations show that phosphide formation hinders the removal of phosphorous from phosphate-bonded refractories.

3. Parameters applied to the thermochemical calculations

The calculations in this report are carried out using FactSage version 8.2. FactSage is a thermochemical calculation software collaboratively developed by Thermfact/CRTC (Montreal, Canada) and GTT-Technologies (Aachen, Germany). The software enables the calculation of the equilibrium concentrations of compounds based on the principle of minimization of the Gibbs free energy [9]. The calculations are made using the FTOxid database.

Five basic ceramic oxides were selected for calculations, based on their relevance to the refractory industry: SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , MgO , CaO , and ZrO_2 . In addition, two minerals were investigated: mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) and andalusite (Al_2SiO_5). The initial system for the simulations was defined as 1,000 moles of H_2 and 1,000 moles of the oxide, at a pressure of 1 atm. For each material, the partial pressure of the gas phase reduction products was plotted as a function of the temperature, from 800 to 1800 °C. Even though experimental results in the literature are typically reported in the form of the percentage weight loss of the refractory material, from a thermodynamics point of view the concentration of solids is irrelevant and does not enter the equilibrium constant. Therefore, provided that there is enough material to be reduced to the equilibrium values, the absolute weight loss of the ceramic will depend on the amount of hydrogen with which it is in contact, but not on the initial mass of the ceramic.

In sequence, the role of pressure and water vapour in the atmosphere is investigated. The calculations are carried out for silica, as it is a common component of the non-basic lining in DRI vessels and is widely known to be more susceptible to reduction than the other oxides. First, the total moles of reduction products for a system comprising 1000 moles of SiO_2 and 1000 moles of H_2 is calculated for temperatures of 800, 900, 1000, and 1100 °C. In sequence, for the temperatures of 900 and 1150 °C (the maximum temperatures at the MIDREX and Energiron/HYL processes, respectively) [9-10], the partial pressure of reduction products is calculated at 1 atm for the presence of up to 5 % water in the atmosphere.

4. Thermodynamic simulations

4.1. The reduction of ceramic oxides as a function of temperature

Figure 1 shows the base 10 logarithm of the total partial pressure of reduction products for SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , MgO , CaO , and ZrO_2 , respectively, exposed to an atmosphere of 100 % H_2 at 1 atm for temperatures from 800 to 1800 °C. The higher the partial pressure of reduction products, the more weight the material loses when exposed to hydrogen – that is, the more intense the corrosion is. It can be seen that the partial pressures of reduction products for the ceramic oxides differ by orders of magnitude. Silica and magnesia present a relatively higher tendency to be reduced, while lime, alumina, and especially zirconia are very resistant to reduction. The stabilities of mullite and andalusite were calculated to be similar to that of silica (Figure 2).

The plots also show a strong dependence of reduction on the temperature, with a very rapid increase of the partial pressure of reduction products with the temperature. For the range of temperatures observed in DRI (around 800 to 1150 °C), it can be seen that the partial pressures are low, even for silica and magnesia. It should be noted, however, that hydrogen is made to flow inside

DRI reactors at extremely high rates, meaning that the refractories will be exposed to a very large volume of H_2 . At the same time, the high gas flow rates imply that equilibrium conditions are difficult to attain.

Figure 1 - Partial pressure of gas phase reduction products of different ceramic oxides exposed to 100% H_2 at 1 atm as a function of temperature (logarithmic scale).

Figure 2 – Partial pressure of gas phase reduction products of silica, mullite, and andalusite exposed to 100 % H_2 at 1 atm as a function of temperature (logarithmic scale).

4.2. The effect of pressure

In sequence, the effect of pressure was investigated for SiO_2 . Figure 3 shows the moles of reduction products in the gas phase at temperatures of 800, 900, 1000, and 1100 °C. Interestingly, at 800 °C, reduction increases with the pressure; at 900 °C, a reversal in this tendency can be observed at around 3 - 4 bar; at 1000 and 1100 °C, the corrosion decreases monotonically with increasing pressure. This behaviour may be explained by Le Chatelier's principle. Since in the reduction reactions, the number of moles of gaseous products is higher than the number of moles of gaseous reactants, an increase in pressure shifts the equilibrium towards the reactants, thereby preventing corrosion. Those results are in line with experimental observations made by Crowley [12]. In the DRI process, the HYL/MIDREX system operates at high pressures, typically above 6 bar [11]. This could have a protective effect on the refractory lining, slowing down corrosion.

Figure 3 - Total moles of gas-phase reduction products for the reduction of silica by hydrogen as a function of pressure at a) 800, b) 900, c) 1000, and d) 1100 °C.

4.3. Reduction in H_2 - H_2O atmospheres

Finally, the effect of water on the reduction of silica was investigated (Table 1). It can be seen that the addition of only 1% water makes corrosion nearly come to a halt. There is a dramatic drop in reduction with 1% addition, and then corrosion slowly continues to decrease as further water is added.

This result is also aligned with the experiments carried out by Crowley, which showed that the presence of water in the atmosphere significantly slows down the reduction of silica by hydrogen [11-12]. Crowley added approximately 25 mmHg of water to the atmosphere in his trials.

Table 1 - Partial pressure of reduction products for the reduction of silica by hydrogen as a function of the water content in the atmosphere at 1 atm and 900 and 1150 °C.

Water content	Partial pressure of reduction products (Pa)	
	900 °C	1150 °C
0%	0.01	1.18
1%	7.48×10^{-8}	1.36×10^{-3}
2%	3.70×10^{-8}	6.7×10^{-4}
3%	2.44×10^{-8}	4.4×10^{-4}
4%	1.81×10^{-8}	3.3×10^{-4}
5%	1.43×10^{-8}	2.6×10^{-4}

5. Conclusion and considerations

This report presented calculations of the equilibrium of different ceramic oxides with hydrogen. They show the strong dependence of reduction with the temperature, and provide a comparison between the stability of different oxides: $\text{SiO}_2 < \text{MgO} < \text{CaO} < \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 < \text{ZrO}_2$. Additionally, according to the thermodynamic calculations, mullite and andalusite should have a level of stability similar to that of silica. It was also observed that an increase in pressure slows down corrosion at certain temperatures. Finally, water was shown to retard the hydrogen corrosion of silica, at a concentration of 5 % in the atmosphere.

It is, however, important to consider that thermodynamics is only part of the story. For a full understanding of the interaction of hydrogen with ceramics, the kinetics of the reactions should also be taken into account and experimentally investigated. Reactions that are shown by thermodynamics to be spontaneous at a given set of conditions (that is, to be accompanied by a negative change in Gibb's free energy, $\Delta G < 0$) may not proceed at a significant rate because of a kinetic barrier, in the form of a high activation energy. Additionally, in the DRI processes the flow rate of H_2 is extremely elevated, and as a consequence, the contact times between a large volume of hydrogen and the refractories are not high enough for a state of equilibrium to be achieved. Nevertheless, the thermodynamic simulations provide valuable information for refractory selection in DRI applications.

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